

Unlocking new frontiers: the versatile potential of the Brazilian Multipurpose Reactor

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ABSTRACT

The multipurpose nature of nuclear research reactors has been investigated. This class of reactors has gained momentum within the international community, given the multiple benefits of nuclear technology in medicine, agriculture, industry, and the development of new materials, being characterized by the simultaneous use of several applications. In this context, Brazil has joined the group of countries with multipurpose reactor projects. The Brazilian Multipurpose Reactor (RMB) will be Brazil's new neutron source, with a thermal power of 30 MW, with a core flux on the order of $\phi = 4 \times 10^{14}$ n/cm²s and a power density of 312.5 W/cm³, ensuring the production of radioisotopes, material and fuel irradiation testing, and neutron beam applications. In this work, the demand for neutron fluxes in different irradiation targets is investigated by Monte Carlo simulations under a perturbation caused by a highly neutron-absorbing material, the Gadolinium-157 (Gd-157) isotope. The choice of Gd-147 represents only a test of the reactor's capabilities. The results show that Molybdenum-99 (Mo-99) production is not affected by the Gd-157 target, and the minimum proposed thermal neutron flux for the reactor's activity ($\phi_{min} = 5.1 \times 10^{12}$ n/cm²s) is guaranteed even at maximum operational capacity.

Keywords: multipurpose reactors, Monte Carlo simulations, radioisotopes production.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the growing demand for radioisotopes for nuclear medicine, the need to test new materials for advanced reactors, and the pursuit of scientific innovation, multipurpose nuclear reactors (MNRs) have become strategic infrastructure for countries that invest in technology, health, energy, and defense [1]. Given the diverse range of research reactor applications, safety requirements do not need to be applied uniformly across all reactor types. The manner in which compliance with these requirements is demonstrated may vary significantly between a high-power MNR and a very low-power reactor, for which the radiological risk to facility personnel, the public, and the environment is minimal [2]. Over the past four decades, many proposals for the design of new research reactors have been developed, showing significant progress since the first criticality of Chicago Pile-1 in December 1942 [3]. A compilation of multipurpose research reactors currently in operation or under construction/planning, with power levels above 10 MW, is presented in Table I (this collection complements the data compiled in [3]). Factors such as the high cost of power reactors, the growing need for material testing under irradiation, the increased demand for medical radioisotopes following the international Mo-99 supply crisis in the late 2000s, and the advanced applications of neutron beams in both hard and soft matter studies have driven the development of new multipurpose research reactor projects on a global scale.

The graded approach is a key principle in the nuclear field, enabling the adjustment of safety and design requirements according to the level of risk associated with each activity or component within a facility [1, 2]. In MNRs, the relationship between power, neutron flux, and power density is particularly significant, especially during transient conditions. In these reactors, the spatial distribution of neutron flux tends to be highly non-uniform, with regions of very high flux near the

core and irradiation channels. During a transient event, such as a rapid power change or a reactivity pulse, this distribution dynamically changes, directly impacting the local power density — that is, the amount of energy released per unit volume at specific locations within the core. The relationship between flux and power, which is approximately linear under steady-state conditions (Figure 1) [4], becomes more complex in this context, requiring careful spatial and temporal evaluation to avoid hot spots or damage to experimental targets.

Table I. - Multipurpose research reactors in operation or under construction with power levels above/equal 10 MW and built after 1980.

Country	Name	Power (MW)	Setup type	Reflector	Criticality date
In operation					
Libya	IRT-1	10	Tube	Be	1981
Indonesia	RSG-GAS	30	MTR	Be	1987
Peru	RP-10	10	MTR	Be, Graphite	1988
Japan	IRR-3 M	20	MTR	D ₂ O	1990
Korea	HANARO	30	Rod	D ₂ O	1991
Algeria	ES-SALAM	15	Rod	Graphite, D ₂ O	1992
Egypt	ETR-2	22	MTR	D ₂ O	1997
Germany	FRM-II	20	Involute plate	D ₂ O	2004
Australia	OPAL	20	MTR	D ₂ O	2006
China	CARR	60	MTR	D ₂ O	2010
Under construction or planned					
France	RJH	100	Curved plate	Be	Construction
India	MPPRR	20	MTR	D ₂ O	Planned
South Africa	MPR	30	MTR	Be	Planned
Netherlands	PALLAS	25	MTR	D ₂ O	Construction
Russian	MBIR	150	vibroMOX	-	Construction
Argentina	RA-10	30	Plate	D ₂ O	Construction
Brazil	RMB	30	MTR	Be/ D ₂ O	Construction

Configured as a multipurpose reactor proposal, RMB (Brazilian Multipurpose Reactor) is a strategic facility designed to meet Brazil's growing demands in research, radioisotope production, and nuclear technological development [5].

2. THE BRAZILIAN MULTIPURPOSE REACTOR

RMB will be an open pool type reactor with 30 MW power located in Iperó, a municipality about 100 Km from São Paulo, Brazil. Its civil construction works in 2025 and is expected to reach criticality by 2032. The main objective of the project is to make Brazil self-sufficient in radiopharmaceuticals through the production of radioisotopes. In addition, the RMB will also be capable of testing and characterizing nuclear fuels and structural materials, material irradiation for advanced research in various scientific disciplines, and the applications with neutron beams [6-9]. Through these objectives, RMB aims to enhance Brazil's technological development, and international competitiveness in the nuclear sector. Its radioisotope production includes a wide range of products, with emphasis on Mo-99 — which accounts for 85% of national demand— as well as Iridium-192 (Ir-192), Iodine-131 (I-131), Iodine-125 (I-125), Lutetium-177 (Lu-177), among others [5].

Figure 1. Relationship between power density, neutron flux, and reactor power [17]. It is observed that the gray rectangle corresponds to the requirements of modern multipurpose research reactors.

The RMB core will be configured in a 5×5 arrangement and will comprise 23 fuel elements made of U_3Si_2 dispersion-type in Aluminum (Al), with a Uranium (U) density of up to 3.5 gU/cm^3 and an enrichment of 19.75% by weight of U-235, and two positions available for materials irradiation devices. This compact and efficient arrangement is designed to ensure high neutron flux at the core of $4 \times 10^{14} \text{ n/cm}^2\text{s}$, optimizing both radioisotope production and material irradiation experiments. The core is cooled and moderated by light water, with a downward forced flow and redundant cooling systems, ensuring thermal safety even under intensive operational conditions. The RMB design includes a Cold Neutron Source (CNS) consisting of 18 liters of Liquid Ortho Deuterium at 23 K, located approximately 50 cm from the reactor core. The reactor's CNS will be responsible for moderating thermal neutrons, producing high-brightness beams and accessing neutrons with energies on the order of 3 meV.

The purpose of this work is to present details of RMB and to discuss the versatility of its multipurpose potential. The demand for high neutron flux in all applications of a multipurpose research reactor can reduce the efficiency of physical processes such as neutron scattering experiments and chemical processes such as the production of radioisotopes with sufficient activity for medical and industrial applications. Therefore, we developed a methodology capable of evaluating the multipurpose nature of a research reactor through Monte Carlo simulations. We simulated neutron transport within the RMB reflector vessel using the MCNP6 [10] code and analyzed the neutron flux at critical positions—defined here as irradiation points furthest from the core—used for the production of Mo-99. To assess the reactor's sensitivity to parallel process demands, we filled all irradiation units with Ir-191 and TeO_2 targets at maximum load. In addition, we simulated neutron absorption by dispersing Gd-157 (an element with a high neutron absorption cross-section, $\sigma_{abs} = 2.54 \times 10^5 \text{ barn}$ [11]) in 6061 Al-alloy plates located in the dummy position. By varying the Gd-157 concentration (α), we were able to evaluate the neutron flux at critical positions, thereby suggesting a balance limit for the reactor's multipurpose capabilities. Given that the target's volume is the sum of the Al and Gd-157 volumes, $V_{target} = V_{Al} + V_{Gd-157} = 10.4 \text{ cm}^3$, the number of Gd-157 and Al atoms are

$$N_{Gd-157} = \frac{\alpha V_{target} d_{Gd-157}}{M_{Gd-157}}, \quad N_{Al} = \frac{\beta V_{target} d_{Al}}{M_{Al}}, \quad (1)$$

where $\alpha + \beta = 1$, d_{Gd-157} , M_{Gd-157} , d_{Al} , M_{Al} are the densities and molar masses of Gd-157 and Al, respectively. The 6061 Al-alloy, used in fuel assembly cladding, has a density of 2.71 g/cm^3 and consists predominantly of Al at 97.86% by weight.

3. MONTE CARLO SIMULATIONS

RMB is equipped with three Out-of-Core Irradiation Facilities (OCIF) positions for producing Ir-192 for medical and industrial applications. The target's geometry—either seeds or pellets—is critical for its final application. We modeled both configurations to assess their impact. The seed model (S) consisted of 100 small cylinders ($D = 1.9$ mm, $H = 2.0$ mm), while the pellet model (P) used 72 larger discs ($D = 2.7$ mm, $H = 18.0$ mm). Both were simulated within a standard Al holder ($D = 31$ mm, $H = 94$ mm). Our preliminary simulations revealed that the neutron flux is not globally affected by the choice of target geometry. This provides us the flexibility to use a simplified model that respects the maximum target load, which is appropriate for our study's focus on the reactor's maximum production limit. The TeO_2 targets, in turn, are modeled as cylinders with a 22 mm diameter and a 75 mm height, with each target being individually inserted into one of the 5 irradiation positions. The assemblies for Mo-99 production consist of a holder that secures multiple targets. Specifically, each holder contains four targets enclosed together within one capsule. Three such assemblies are loaded into each Mo-99 irradiation tube. The target's core ("meat") is a UAl_2 -Al dispersion, while the cladding, holder, and capsule are all made of 6061 Al-alloy. Each target has a total U mass of 8.962 g, which includes 1.77 g of U-235. The resulting U density in the target core is approximately 2.388 g/cm³. A diagram showing the eleven irradiation positions for Mo-99 target production, the five positions for TeO_2 targets, the three positions for Ir-191 targets, and the dummy position containing Gd-157 is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Reflector tank and target positions: (#1–#11) Mo-99 production, (#12–#16) TeO_2 , (#17) dummy containing Gd-157, and (#18–#20) for Ir-192 production.

The MCNP model is based on evaluated nuclear data from the **ENDF/B-VII.0** library, as confirmed by the XSDIR file entries (e.g., from `endf/b-vii.0 njoy99.248`). All continuous-energy cross sections (70c and associated datasets) are generated at 293.6 K (20 °C). Thermal scattering $S(\alpha, \beta)$ data at 293.6 K are consistently assigned to the relevant moderator and reflector materials. The treatment **lwtr.10t** is used for hydrogen bound in light water (**1001.70c**), corresponding to materials 30000, 80000, and 80013. The library **hwtr.10t** is applied to deuterium in heavy water (**1002.70c**), associated with material 80000. For beryllium (**4009.70c**), used in material 80012, the **be.10t** dataset is employed. In addition, **dortho.10t** is assigned to ortho-deuterium (**1002.70c**), corresponding to material 80001. Criticality calculations are carried out using the card **KCODE 1e6 1 50 1050**, which defines 1,000,000 neutron histories per cycle, 1 initial inactive cycle for source convergence, 50 active cycles for statistical accumulation of tallies, and storage of up to 1050 cycles to support convergence evaluation. Each simulation required 48 hours and used 48 CPUs (AMD EPYC 7402 processors) from the Coaraci Supercomputer, Campinas, Brazil.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results of the neutron fluxes for all irradiation positions are presented in Table 2, for $\beta = 1$. It can be observed that the irradiation positions behave like points in an interconnected network, where the arrangement of targets seeks a balance between increasing and decreasing the neutron flux in first neighbors. Even in the presence of a target composed entirely of Gd-157, the thermal neutron flux in the targets for Mo-99 production remains above the minimum of $\phi_{\min} = 5.1 \times 10^{12}$ n/cm²s [12].

It can be observed in Figure 3 that there is only a slight alteration on the neutron flux map due the presence of a highly absorbing material. It can also be concluded that the dimensions of the irradiation targets guarantee the stability of the reactor's operation, ensuring the production of radioisotopes, irradiation of materials, and extraction of neutron beams.

Table II. Results obtained for the case $\beta = 1$, that is, the dummy in position 17 is made only of Aluminum (%Gd-157 = 0). Maximum relative error = 3%.

OCIF	Thermal Flux (n/cm ² s)	Epithermal Flux (n/cm ² s)	Fast Flux (n/cm ² s)	Total Flux (n/cm ² s)
Mo-#1	1.20734E+14	3.70124E+13	2.64223E+13	1.84168E+14
Mo-#2	1.16024E+14	3.84878E+13	2.62800E+13	1.80792E+14
Mo-#3	1.08016E+14	3.13382E+13	2.35073E+13	1.62862E+14
Mo-#4	1.08421E+14	3.12181E+13	2.31132E+13	1.62752E+14
Mo-#5	1.09583E+14	3.81999E+13	2.40411E+13	1.71824E+14
Mo-#6	9.75348E+13	3.67532E+13	2.24464E+13	1.56734E+14
Mo-#7	8.52491E+13	3.09946E+13	1.96175E+13	1.35861E+14
Mo-#8	7.85337E+13	2.62302E+13	1.76633E+13	1.22427E+14
Mo-#9	7.38239E+13	2.52416E+13	1.69315E+13	1.15997E+14
Mo-#10	7.79808E+13	2.58087E+13	1.78876E+13	1.21677E+14
Mo-#11	9.21167E+13	2.85964E+13	2.05439E+13	1.41257E+14
TeO ₂ -#12	1.38526E+14	3.10240E+13	4.38596E+12	1.73936E+14
TeO ₂ -#13	1.21725E+14	2.54617E+13	4.31922E+12	1.51506E+14
TeO ₂ -#14	1.20446E+14	2.63297E+13	4.52606E+12	1.51302E+14
TeO ₂ -#15	1.27384E+14	3.09566E+13	4.87621E+12	1.63217E+14
TeO ₂ -#16	1.56115E+14	4.66314E+13	6.38666E+12	2.09133E+14
dummy-#17	2.08290E+14	5.37563E+13	5.99008E+12	2.68037E+14
Ir-#18	3.83463E+13	6.40764E+13	1.14767E+13	1.13899E+14
Ir-#19	3.99135E+13	6.72665E+13	1.19737E+13	1.19154E+14
Ir-#20	4.05584E+13	6.58226E+13	1.13484E+13	1.17729E+14

Individual results for the three different irradiated materials can be seen in Figures 4-7, representing the ratio between the thermal neutron fluxes at the irradiation positions in the absence ($\beta = 1$) and presence of Gd-157 in the dummy, respectively, in function of Al concentration (β).

The fit in Figure 7 allows us to obtain a relation for the thermal neutron flux ($\phi_{\text{dummy}}(\beta)$) passing through the dummy as a function of its composition, that is, the percentage of Al and Gd-157, with $R^2 = 0.9999$,

$$\phi_{\text{dummy}}(\beta) = \frac{7.54674 \times 10^{13}}{4.65217e^{-1.24\beta} - 1}. \quad (2)$$

Figure 3. Neutron flux map obtained using MCNP6 for the RMB reflector tank ($\beta = 1$).

Figure 4. Results for the target positions of Mo-99 production.

It is interesting to note that the resulting expression (2) is the typical form for the problem of flux through a body as a function of its thickness [13], which in our case is emulated by the β parameter.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Although Gd-157 has a high cross section, no irradiation point undergoes sufficient changes to invalidate the final objective of the reactor. The maximum perturbation found (27.48%) at position #6 does not drastically affect the production of Mo-99, given that $\phi_{\min} = 5.1 \times 10^{12}$ n/cm²s. This is an interesting result, as it allows the RMB to propose irradiating elements with high neutron absorption without compromising parallel activities of the reactor. That is, RMB stands out in the radioisotope production scenario due to the great potential for applications of MNRs.

Figure 5. Results for the target positions for I-131 production.

Figure 6. Results for the target positions for Ir-192 production.

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Figure 7. Results of dummy position.

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